

THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF CRITICAL THINKING OF STUDENTS IN THE CONDITIONS OF INNOVATION EDUCATION

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In the process of critical thinking, questions are used aimed at analyzing and interpreting information, analyzing ideas, rearranging the stories under study with their own approximate plans.

Critical thinking aosos will consist of three phases (phases), these are:

- Call (call
- Awareness
- Are stages of thinking (reflection).

Critical thinking begins with the stage that it calls a call, during which the interest of students is aroused, the necessary questions are raised, and the reasons for obtaining such knowledge are formed. This is followed by a stage of understanding meaning, during which the O'kors receive an incentive to seek, which they also get used to in some Holls.

The stage of thinking is considered a culmination, during which students are asked to summarize their knowledge, compare what they have learned with what they know before that, assess their questions according to what level they have received answers to (and formulate new questions depending on the need), apply what they know to even greater problems, debate and defend the ARSS they have learned. The importance of the call stage is such that new knowledge in it, striving for a goal of its own independent choice, will be very strong. At the call stage, several important types of knowledge-giving activities are carried out.

First, the learner is actively involved in restoring what he knows about this topic. This forces him to analyze his knowledge and begin to think about a subject that will soon be considered atapsively. After the other two stages are explained, the importance of the initial action becomes clearer. To help students think about what they know, to generate interest will come true. Students determine the level of their knowledge to which new knowledge can be added. If knowledge is obtained in the context of those that a person knows and understands, it is thorough. If information is given to the reader without contacting previous knowledge, it will quickly disappear. The educational process is the process of connecting new ones with known ones. The new imagination of the reader is built on the basis of his previous knowledge and imagination. By helping students regain their previous knowledge and imagination, a broad framework can be laid for a long-term understanding of new information. The second purpose of the call phase is to activate the learners. Education is an active activity that requires aspiration. Students must actively participate in the educational process so that they have a conscious, thorough understanding of new information and a critical approach to new information. The reader is activated by thinking on the basis of a set goal and expressing his thoughts in his own words. The demonstration of knowledge (to oneself and to a partner) occurs with the help of oral or written speech, through active thinking. Thus, the lgari acquired knowledge is brought to the level of awareness. Now they can be the basis for

mastering new knowledge. This gives the O'corans the opportunity to effectively link new information with what they knew before, because a context has emerged for understanding.

The third goal of the call stage is that there is an interest in considering the proposed topic and the goal is determined. The presence of interest and purpose further increases the activity of students. Goal determination is most important in education. The goal will be of two types: the goal set by the teacher or in the proposed text, and the goal chosen by the student independently. Independently selected goals will be stronger than those that are forced from the outside. Personal interest determines a personal goal. If there is no stable interest, the motivation of O'cuw's activities decreases. In general the reader achieves real understanding by receiving answers to his questions. The importance of the stage of perception. In the awareness phase, new information is associated with information activated in the call phase. The main task of this stage is, first, to apply the inertia of interest and movement, activity, created in the call stage. His second important task is to apply his aspirations to observe his own understanding in students.

The subject's knowledge of internal processes and states by himself is called reflectivity (sometimes meta-cognition). Reflection (Latin reflexio - retrograde) is a philosophical concept that refers to his meditation on the changes taking place in the mind of individ. Reflection is not only the self-understanding of the subject, but it also refers to the "reflectance", its individual characteristics, the expression of its response to influence, and the clarification of perceptions of cognition, etc . The most important function of the phase is to achieve an understanding of the new learning material. Active students hear the message and usually ask questions or write down what they do not understand for later identification. Sluggish woodpeckers do not, nor do they think about the confusion, misunderstandings that have arisen, or about something that has not been understood. When students observe their own understanding, they compare new information with their own perceptions, consciously associating new ones with what was previously known. They build bridges between old and new knowledge to create new understanding.

The importance of the stage of thinking (reasoning). In this phase, knowledge is strengthened and a different (Fuller) imagination is formed in relation to the previous phases on the issue under study and leads to an increase in "readability". Such changes can only occur when the student achieves his or her academic goal. Thus, in this phase, the transfer of the reader from a lower level of reading to a higher level of it occurs. This is reflected in the reader's ability to express new ideas and information in their own word. Students will better remember what they like more. At the thinking stage, it is planned to achieve several important goals. In the first place, the O'kors should try to express new thoughts and information in their own words. If you need to remember - you will forget. If you need to understand - you will remember. How long the educational outcomes are maintained as well as the level of understanding is different in different people. A personal understood context arises when one expresses and rearranges the intelligible in one's own words. The second goal of the thinking phase is a lively exchange of thoughts between students, which allows them to expand their vocabulary as well as get to know the imagination of other students. Changing critical thinking intensifies in an environment where different thoughts are encouraged. Then students can take them into account and build their own imagination.

The basics of critical thinking create conditions for the teacher in such a way that, as a result, he achieves the following:

- activates student thinking;
- separates the purpose of education (students) ;
- provides an opportunity for active discussion;
- increases interest in reading;
- provides active training activities;
- promotes change;
- encourages reasoning;
- gives O'corans the opportunity to listen to different opinions;
- helps students ask their questions;
- allows the reader to realize himself;
- ensures that information is processed by students;
- provides opportunities for critical thinking in students .

As the class becomes a student partnership society, different opinions develop. Students are active, and the teacher is considered a partner. Students take an active O'cuw pose. All this leads to a change of personality, which is a condition for gaining solid knowledge. The student remains a teacher in a certain sense. The O's perform certain parts of the teacher's activities. The class becomes a partnership society.

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